

Academic Guidelines and Recommendations for Integrating Green Coding Aspects into Curricula of Higher Education

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Supplementary Material C – Full Integration - Exemplary Structure of a Study Program

Module name	Module Type	Description
Introduction to Computer Science (ICS)	1	Overview of computer science principles, algorithms, and programming fundamentals. This module provides students with a comprehensive introduction to the field of computer science, covering topics such as data structures, algorithms, and the foundations of programming. Students will gain a solid understanding of the key concepts and theories that underpin modern computing.
Mathematics for Computer Science (MCS)	1	Mathematical concepts and techniques relevant to computer science, including discrete mathematics and calculus. This module equips students with the necessary mathematical tools and problem-solving skills required for various areas of computer science. Topics covered include logic, sets, functions, graph theory, and calculus.

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Sustainable Development and Environmental Studies	2	Introduction to sustainability principles, environmental challenges, and the role of technology in sustainability. This module explores the fundamental principles of sustainable development and examines our planet's environmental challenges. Students will learn how technology affects the environment and how computing may aid in developing sustainable solutions. The module encourages critical thinking and raises awareness of the importance of ethical and environmentally conscious decision-making.
Introduction to Sustainable Computing (ISC)	2	This module introduces students to Sustainable Computing, green IT practices, energy-efficient computing, and green coding, focusing on ecological concerns and minimizing energy consumption and environmental impact in software development.
Programming I (PROG I)	3	Fundamentals of programming, coding practices, and problem-solving. This module provides a hands-on introduction to programming, focusing on integrating sustainability principles. Students will learn the fundamentals of programming logic, algorithm design, and coding practices. Through practical exercises and coding projects, they will develop problem-solving skills and gain confidence in building functional software applications while keeping sustainability in mind as a key aspect.
Data Structures and Algorithms (DSA)	1	In-depth study of data structures and algorithm design, focusing on efficient and sustainable algorithms. This module builds upon the foundational knowledge of data structures and algorithms gained in earlier courses. Students will delve deeper into analyzing and implementing data structures such as linked lists, trees, graphs, and hash tables, emphasizing memory efficiency and performance optimization.
Software Architecture (SA)	1	Principles of object-oriented programming, design patterns, and their application. This module focuses on the architectural aspects of software development, emphasizing the importance of well-structured, scalable, and maintainable systems. Special attention will be given to designing software systems that can adapt to changing requirements and can be easily maintained and extended over time.
Sustainable Software Engineering (SSE)	3	In this module, students will be taught various approaches to optimize code and profile performance. Furthermore, the course will encompass methodologies for enhancing software quality and maintainability through software testing, debugging, and refactoring. Considering the significance of eco-friendly software design in reducing the environmental impact of the technology industry, the module incorporates the GREEN-SOFT framework and other sustainable software engineering principles into its practical applications.
Programming II (PROG II)	3	Advanced programming concepts and software development techniques, Object-oriented programming. This module explores advanced programming concepts and techniques based on the foundational programming knowledge gained in the earlier courses. Students will learn about inheritance, polymorphism, encapsulation, and other Object-Oriented Programming (OOP) principles to write modular, flexible, and maintainable code. Students will learn about design patterns, such as MVC (Model-View-Controller) and Singleton, to build modular and reusable code. Additionally, the module will cover topics such as multithreading, concurrency, and memory management to develop efficient and responsive software applications.
Measuring Energy Consumption in Software Systems (MECSS)	2	Employing tools like the green SDK or SPEEL methods to measure and analyze energy consumption in software systems. This module focuses on advanced techniques for measuring and analyzing energy consumption in software applications. Students will learn about software energy profiling tools, such as the green Software Development Kit (SDK) and the Software Power Estimation and Evaluation Kit (SPEEL), to assess the energy footprint of software systems. Through practical exercises and experiments, students will gain hands-on experience in measuring power consumption during code execution and identifying energy-intensive segments of applications.

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Database Systems (DS)	3	Introduction to database management systems and data modeling. This module covers the fundamental principles of database systems. Students will learn about database models, such as relational and NoSQL databases, and explore techniques for designing efficient and eco-friendly databases. Topics include data normalization, indexing, and query optimization to reduce energy consumption and enhance data retrieval performance. Additionally, students will gain hands-on experience in data modeling for sustainability, ensuring that database structures align with the principles of Green Computing.
Web Development (WD)	3	Web technologies and sustainable web development practices, including optimizing web performance and reducing data transfer. This module focuses on web development technologies and practices contributing to a sustainable digital ecosystem. Students will learn about front-end and back-end web technologies and explore techniques for building energy-efficient and resource-conscious web applications. Topics include web performance optimization, data compression, caching, and content delivery networks to reduce data transfer and improve website loading times. Students will also gain insights into web design, considering factors such as user experience and accessibility.
Operating Systems and Networking (OSN)	3	Study of operating systems and networking concepts, considering energy-efficient protocols and resource management. This module provides an in-depth examination of operating systems and networking from the sustainability perspective. Students will explore the internals of operating systems, analyzing their resource management and power-saving features. Networking concepts will include energy-efficient protocols like IPv6 and strategies for reducing network traffic and latency. Additionally, students will gain practical knowledge of virtualization and containerization to optimize resource utilization and energy consumption in cloud computing environments.
Energy-Efficient Programming Fundamentals (EEP)	2	Evaluating the importance of energy-efficient programming and its impact on resource consumption in software projects. This module emphasizes the significance of energy-efficient programming practices in achieving sustainability goals. Students will learn about the energy consumption profiles of different programming languages, algorithms, tools, and techniques for measuring and optimizing energy usage in software. The module will cover topics like profiling code for energy efficiency, selecting appropriate data structures, and employing low-power computing techniques. Through practical exercises and real-world application analysis, students will understand how programming decisions can impact energy consumption and overall
Software Testing and Quality Assurance (STQA)	1	Techniques for software testing and quality assurance. This module equips students with the essential skills to ensure the quality and reliability of software applications. Students will learn various software testing methodologies, including unit testing, integration testing, functional testing and acceptance testing. Students will also learn techniques for automating software development processes through continuous integration and deployment.
Mobile App Development (MAD)	3	Mobile application development and optimizing mobile apps for energy efficiency. This module focuses on mobile app development, considering the specific challenges and opportunities for Sustainable Computing on mobile platforms. Students will learn about mobile development frameworks, user interface design for mobile devices, and mobile app optimization techniques. Topics include battery-efficient programming, data usage reduction, and adaptive performance based on device capabilities.
Cloud Computing and Virtualization (CCV)	3	Understanding cloud computing and virtualization technologies, including sustainable cloud practices. This module introduces students to cloud computing and virtualization, essential components of modern computing infrastructures. Students will learn about cloud service and deployment models (public, private, hybrid). Special focus will be on sustainable cloud practices, such as energy-efficient data centers, dynamic resource allocation, and server consolidation. Students will also explore containerization technologies, like Docker, to optimize application deployment in cloud environments.
Ethics and Social Responsibility in Computing (ESRC)	2	This module delves into the ethical implications of technology and computing practices in the context of sustainability. Students will examine ethical frameworks and codes of conduct in computing, considering their impact on sustainable decision-making. The module will address technology-related social and environmental concerns like data privacy, algorithmic biases, and electronic waste management.

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Life cycle Analysis (LCA)	2	In this module, students will learn the principles and methodologies of life cycle analysis (LCA), including goal definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and interpretation. They will apply LCA to various technology products and computing systems to understand their ecological footprint and identify opportunities for sustainable improvements. The module will emphasize the role of LCA in decision-making processes for environmentally conscious design and responsible consumption of technology.
Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AIML)	3	Introduction to AI and ML with a focus on their application in Sustainable Computing solutions. This module provides an overview of artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques and their relevance to Sustainable Computing. Students will learn about popular AI and ML algorithms, including neural networks, decision trees, and clustering methods. The module will explore how these technologies can be leveraged to address environmental challenges and promote sustainable practices. Topics may include smart energy management, predictive maintenance, and optimization of AI and ML resource usage.
Human-Computer Interaction (HCI)	1	Designing sustainable user interfaces and considering user behavior for energy-efficient interactions. This module focuses on the design of human-computer interfaces that prioritize energy efficiency and user experience. Students will study user-centered design principles and explore techniques for designing eco-friendly user interfaces. Topics include energy-aware interface elements, adaptive user interactions, and user behavior analysis to optimize energy consumption. The module will also cover accessibility and inclusivity considerations in sustainable user interface design.
Cybersecurity and Data Privacy (CSDP)	1	Study of cybersecurity and data privacy issues, including securing Sustainable Computing systems. This module addresses the critical aspect of cybersecurity and data privacy in Sustainable Computing. Students will learn about common security threats and vulnerabilities in computing systems and explore strategies for securing software applications and infrastructure. Topics may include encryption techniques, secure coding practices, and network security measures. Additionally, the module will cover data privacy and compliance regulations related to Sustainable Computing applications.
Project - Sustainable Computing (SC)	3	A major project where students apply their knowledge to develop Sustainable Computing solutions. This project-based learning module is designed to help students use their new-found knowledge and abilities. Working individually or in teams, students will identify a real-world problem related to sustainability and propose a computing solution to address it. The project may involve designing energy-efficient software, optimizing existing systems for sustainability, or exploring innovative Green Computing technologies. Throughout the project, students will be guided by mentors and faculty members to ensure the successful implementation of their Sustainable Computing solutions.
Future Advances in Software Sustainability (FASS)	2	The module explores cutting-edge research and emerging trends in Sustainable Computing. Students will explore advanced topics and innovative solutions addressing the growing demand for eco-friendly and energy-efficient software systems. The module covers the latest developments in Green Computing technologies, such as quantum computing, bio-inspired algorithms, and neuromorphic computing, which have the potential to revolutionize sustainable software design and execution. Additionally, students will explore futuristic concepts like energy-harvesting computing, self-sustainable systems, and carbon-neutral data centers. Through lectures and seminars, students will gain a forward-looking perspective on Sustainable Computing and prepare themselves for the challenges and opportunities of tomorrow's green technology landscape.
Industry Project (IP)	3	This module provides students a unique opportunity to gain practical experience by working on real-world Sustainable Computing projects in collaboration with industry partners. Under the guidance of experienced professionals, students will actively contribute to designing, developing, and implementing energy-efficient software solutions or optimizing existing systems for sustainability. Projects may involve creating green algorithms, devising power-aware data center strategies, or improving the energy efficiency of cloud-based applications. Students will refine their teamwork, problem-solving, and project-management skills throughout the project. By engaging with industry experts, students will also deepen their understanding of the challenges and considerations involved in delivering environmentally responsible technology solutions.
Thesis	3	Students will conduct individual research on a specific Sustainable Computing topic of their choice. With guidance from faculty advisors, students will define research objectives, conduct a literature review, and devise a research methodology to investigate their chosen topic comprehensively. The research may explore various dimensions of Sustainable Computing, such as assessing the environmental impact of different software architectures, proposing new energy-efficient algorithms, or analyzing the carbon footprint of cloud computing services. Through rigorous investigation and analysis, students will contribute original insights to the field of Sustainable Computing. The thesis will be presented in a comprehensive document that showcases the research findings, methodologies, and conclusions. This final module will demonstrate the student's mastery of Sustainable Computing principles and ability to apply critical thinking and research skills to tackle complex environmental challenges in technology.